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iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

D4.1 – AI-driven Analysis Onsite for Monitoring Combined with Advanced Representations v1

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ABOUT iDRIVING

iDriving, a 3-year Horizon-funded project, unites 17 European partners in a mission to enhance road safety. The project focuses on transforming urban and secondary rural road infrastructure through innovation. It aligns with the EU's goals for smart transport and actively embraces emerging technologies. Key areas include enhancing driver behaviour, improving infrastructure safety, and empowering first responders. Through a comprehensive Safety Criteria Catalogue, innovative sensors, AI-based warnings, and a Digital Twin, iDriving paves the way for safer roads.

The iDriving consortium consists of the following partners:

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2	POLYTECHNEIO KRITIS	TUC	EL

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5	FUNDACION TEKNIKER	TEKNIKER	ES
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8	ACCELIGENCE LTD	ACCELI	CY
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Executive summary

This deliverable presents the first technical outcomes of WP4 Intelligent Edge Computing and Monitoring for Safer and Well-maintained Roads during the initial reporting period (M03-M18). It summarises the development of real-time on-site computing solutions that integrate advanced AI-driven analysis, behavioural understanding, environmental monitoring and 3D scene representation. The work conducted in this period establishes the foundation for the intelligent monitoring components that will be integrated into the iDriving pilots and digital ecosystem in subsequent phases.

Overview of Objectives

The primary objective of D4.1 is to deliver preliminary versions of the core WP4 modules that enable real-time processing and interpretation of road infrastructure, road-use behaviour and environmental conditions. These components support:

- On-site visual analysis through embedded AI models.
- Behavioural detection of unsafe or non-compliant road-user actions.
- Automated identification of road defects and maintenance needs.
- High-resolution environmental monitoring relevant to road safety.
- AI-based 3D reconstruction and representation for improved situational understanding.

These achievements provide the first operational capabilities needed to support proactive safety measures, predictive maintenance and dynamic updates of digital twins.

Key Technological Advancements and Innovations

Several technological innovations have been delivered in this first period:

- Real-time edge analytics pipeline integrating detection, tracking and video stabilisation, optimised through quantisation and parallel processing to run efficiently on Jetson and GPU platforms.
- Behavioural analysis framework capable of transforming low-level detections into interpretable traffic violations, including zebra-crossing misuse, improper lane usage and failure-to-yield, fully integrated into the Kafka streaming ecosystem.
- Automated road defect detection using YOLOv11 models, enhanced with data augmentation and explainability (EigenCAM), achieving near-real-time performance and robust detection across diverse conditions.

- Environmental monitoring workflow with containerised WRF/WRFDA systems, real-time data ingestion pipelines and configuration of high-resolution domains for Thessaloniki and Karlovac.
- Advanced 3D scene reconstruction using 3D Gaussian Splatting (Splatfacto), validated on benchmark and real-world UAV datasets, and enabling semantic enrichment from defect detection outputs.

Together, these technologies deliver a multi-layered, AI-enhanced monitoring system capable of supporting safety-critical decision-making.

Relevance to overall Project Goals

The results achieved in D4.1 directly contribute to iDriving's mission of improving road safety and infrastructure quality across urban and rural environments. The components developed in WP4 strengthen:

- Early detection of risks, including unsafe behaviour, surface degradation and hazardous environmental conditions.
- Efficient and proactive maintenance, supported by automated defect identification and integration with the digital twin developed in WP5.
- Smart V2I-enabled safety services, thanks to real-time on-site analytics that reduce latency and bandwidth demand.
- Pilot readiness, as the vI modules provide the technical basis for integration, validation and refinement in WP6.

Overall, this deliverable marks a significant step toward the deployment of intelligent, data-driven and safety-oriented infrastructure management within the iDriving ecosystem.

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Glossary

Acronym/Term	Full Name
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AI-driven analysis	Analysis performed using machine-learning or deep-learning models in real time.
API	Application Programming Interface
Behavioural detector	Algorithm that identifies driving behaviours or traffic violations.
CNN	Convolutional Neural Network
COLMAP	Structure-from-Motion pipeline used for camera pose estimation
DT (Digital Twin)	Virtual representation of a physical infrastructure that updates dynamically with data.
Edge computing	Local data processing on embedded devices close to the sensors.
EigenCAM	Explainability technique that generates activation maps for CNN-based models.
FPS	Frames Per Second

GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
H3DGS	Hierarchical 3D Gaussian Splatting
Jetson	NVIDIA Jetson embedded computing platform
Kafka	Distributed message-streaming platform used for WP4 data ingestion and publishing
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
KR	Key Result
Lane misuse	Traffic violation caused by using an incorrect or unauthorised lane
LiDAR	Light Detection And Ranging sensor (used in multimodal approaches)
mAP	Mean Average Precision (main accuracy metric for object detection)
Mip-NeRF 360	High-quality benchmark dataset for 3D reconstruction
ML	Machine Learning
NeRF	Neural Radiance Fields – neural-rendering method for 3D scene reconstruction
PCU / PUC	Pilot Use Case
RGB	Red-Green-Blue image format
RDD2020/RDD2022	Road Damage Dataset (large public benchmark for defects)
Real-time analysis	On-the-fly processing with low latency in the acquisition node
SAM / SAM2	Segment Anything Model – foundation model for universal segmentation
SfM / SLAM	Structure-from-Motion / Simultaneous Localization and Mapping
Splatfacto	Enhanced 3D Gaussian Splatting model (Nerfstudio) used in Task 4.5
UAV	Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (drone)
V2I	Vehicle-to-Infrastructure communication
WRF	Weather Research and Forecasting numerical model
WRFDA	WRF Data Assimilation System
YOLOv8/YOLOv11	“You Only Look Once” family of real-time object detection models
3DGS	3D Gaussian Splatting – fast neural rendering technique for 3D reconstruction

1 Introduction

1.1 Context and objectives

The **iDriving** project is framed within the European need to enhance road safety on urban and secondary roads through advanced digital solutions. Deliverable **D4.1** represents the first milestone of **WP4 – Intelligent Edge Computing and Monitoring for Safer and Well-maintained Roads**, whose purpose is to demonstrate the feasibility of real-time, on-site analysis by integrating AI, computer vision and 3D representations to identify risks, detect incidents and provide information to the V2I ecosystem.

The objective of this document is to:

- Present the initial technical results achieved during the first 18 months (M03–M18) of the project.
- Show the progress in the development of embedded AI modules, visual analysis, intelligent environmental monitoring and advanced 3D generation.
- Position these advances within the overall objectives of the project, contributing to a safer, smarter and more proactive road infrastructure.
- Provide the technical foundation that will enable the integration of these components into the project pilots (WP6) and into the digital ecosystem for prediction and intelligent maintenance (WP5).

Deliverable D4.1 therefore constitutes a first technical version that will allow assessing the system's capabilities prior to the deployment of the second version (D4.2).

1.2 Scope of the Deliverable

This first version of the deliverable:

- Covers the work carried out during the initial period (M03–M18).
- Focuses on the preliminary versions (v1) of the key WP4 components:
 - AI-driven on-site analysis framework (Task 4.1).
 - Behavioural analysis of road users (Task 4.2)
 - Visual analysis for maintenance (Task 4.3).
 - Intelligent monitoring of environmental conditions (Task 4.4).
 - AI-driven 3D scene reconstruction and semantic enhancement for road safety and maintenance monitoring (Task 4.5).
- Does not yet include validation in the final pilots nor full integration within the project ecosystem (WP5 and WP3), which will be addressed in D4.2 and D4.3.
- Provides initial technical evidence, algorithms, architectural design, datasets used, and first quantitative results.

D4.1 provides the foundation for the next WP4 deliverable (D4.2 at M26), which will extend, integrate and validate the components documented in this first version.

1.3 Relation to Other WPs

Deliverable **D4.1** is closely related to:

WP3 – Advanced V2I Data Management and On-site Applications

- WP3 provides the communications infrastructure, sensors and edge nodes where the WP4 algorithms will run.
- The real-time analysis performed in WP4 depends on the data streams generated by the V2I architectures, UAVs, cameras and vehicular systems developed in WP3.
- Several WP4 algorithms (e.g., visual analysis of user behaviour or defect detection) complement the aerial and ground monitoring services implemented in WP3.

WP5 – Dynamic Learning and Digital Twins for Safety and Maintenance

- The results from WP4 feed the digital twins (DTs) and predictive models built in WP5.
- The indicators detected by WP4 (defects, incidents, environmental conditions, behavioural patterns) allow dynamic updates of KPIs and risk models.
- WP5 will use the semantics of the events detected in WP4 to support prediction processes and decision making.

The developments presented in D4.1 are aligned with the integration activities planned with WP3 and WP5 for the period M22-M26, ensuring the compatibility across data acquisition, communication infrastructure and the digital twin components.

1.4 Structure of the Document

The document is structured as follows:

- **Section 2 – Overview of WP4:** objectives, scope and general framework of the work package.
- **Section 3 – Technical Progress:** detailed description of the progress achieved in each WP4 task, including preliminary implementations and results.
- **Section 4 – Summary of Results and Challenges:** synthesis of the status and identified challenges.
- **Section 5 – Conclusions and Next Steps:** next steps towards version 2 of the deliverable.
- **Section 6 – References**
- **Section 7 – Annexes:** supplementary material, architectures, datasets and visual results.

2 Overview of WP4

2.1 WP4 Objectives and rationale

WP4's mission is to develop intelligent edge computing technologies capable of analysing, in real time, the condition of road infrastructure, user behaviour and environmental factors, by combining AI, visual data, sensors and advanced 3D models.

WP4 develops:

- AI-driven analysis for the detection of objects, incidents, behaviours and risks in both urban and rural environments (Task 4.1 and Task 4.2).
- Advanced methods for identifying road defects, surface degradation and maintenance indicators (Task 4.3).
- Systems for monitoring environmental conditions that are relevant to road safety (Task 4.4).
- Innovative 3D reconstruction and AI-based scene generation technologies that enhanced situational understanding and enrich the safety and maintenance ecosystem (Task 4.5).

WP4 is therefore a key pillar in achieving the project's vision: early warnings, efficient maintenance and intelligent monitoring of road infrastructure.

2.2 Contributors and Roles

WP4 brings together several partners with complementary expertise, each contributing specialised capabilities aligned with the objectives of the WP4.

CERTH, as WP coordinator and leader of Task 4.1, 4.3 and 4.5, drives the developments in real-time visual monitoring, road-defect detection and advanced 3D scene reconstruction. CERTH is responsible for edge-based deep learning models for object and incident detection, road defect analysis and AI-driven 3D scene generation, as well as the integration of these algorithms into low-latency edge devices.

TEKNIKER leads Task T4.2, focusing on AI-powered behavioural analysis and early detection of risky situations. The team develops multisensory algorithms combining visual and inertial data to detect anomalous trajectories, dangerous driving patterns and traffic violations. Tekniker also supports integration with V2I nodes and hosts one of the project pilots where WP4 components will be deployed and validated.

DREVEN, leader of Task 4.4, contributes expertise in environmental monitoring, providing the modelling framework, data pipelines and high-resolution weather analysis needed to support real-time hazard detection.

UNI.EIFFEL contributes to scenario analysis, sensor modelling and evaluation methodologies, supporting the robustness of visual and behavioural analysis across complex road environments for Task 4.1 and 4.2.

TUC supports the work in visual analysis and contributes knowledge in sensing pipelines and UAV-based data acquisition, enabling complex scenario reconstruction and multimodal data support for Tasks T4.1 and T4.3

MobiLysis contributes knowledge in UAV-based data acquisition for T4.1 and in multimodal behavioural analytics for T4.2.

ACCELI contributes to UAV-based data acquisition, path-planning optimisation and the preparation of datasets used for 3D reconstruction and validation activities in Task 4.5.

INFRA PLAN supports the generation of road-surface datasets and provides expertise in infrastructure condition monitoring, contributing key data and validation scenarios for Task 4.3 and 4.5.

Together, these partners deliver the combined expertise – spanning embedded AI, computer vision, UAV technologies, environmental sensing and 3D modelling – required to develop the intelligent edge-computing framework of WP4.

2.3 Alignment with Project KPIs

The KPIs associated with WP4 address the performance of edge AI models, behavioural analysis, environmental monitoring, 3D reconstruction and road defect detection. Deliverable D4.1 provides the first technical version of the algorithms, datasets, architectures and preliminary results required to demonstrate progress towards these indicators.

The table (Table 1) below summarises how each WP4 task contributes to the project’s Key Results (KR) and their corresponding KPIs.

Table 1. WP4 Task contributions to KRs and KPIs

KRs	KPIs	WP Tasks	Contribution of D4.1
KR4 – Accurate and efficient detection of objects of interest on-site	KPI4.1, KPI4.2, KPI4.3, KPI4.4	T4.1	KPI4.1 is addressed through the development of detection models supporting more than 15 distinct object classes across the evaluated scenarios, exceeding the target of >10 classes. KPI4.2 is supported by achieved detection performance, with mAP scores ranging between 80–88% across the trained YOLOv8/YOLOv11 models, thereby meeting the accuracy requirement. In relation to

			<p>KPI4.3, real-time processing capabilities have been demonstrated with ~11 FPS performance on Jetson-based edge platforms and ~25 FPS on GPU systems, fulfilling both edge and non-edge targets. KPI4.4, which concerns latency reduction through edge deployment, has not yet been quantitatively evaluated, as corresponding measurements are planned for upcoming integrated tests. Overall, the progress achieved during M03–M18 establishes a solid basis for meeting the relevant KPIs during pilot deployments.</p>
<p>KR5 – Efficient abnormal driving pattern and traffic violation detection</p>	<p>KPI5.1, KPI5.2, KPI5.3, KPI5.4</p>	<p>T4.2</p>	<p>Development module: behavioural detectors (zebra crossing, lane misuse, failure to yield) with 80–87% accuracy on simulated data; integration with perception module; real-time operation demonstrated.</p>
<p>KR6 – Accurate monitoring of microclimates and real-time environmental analysis</p>	<p>KPI6.1, KPI6.2</p>	<p>T4.4</p>	<p>Task 4.4 supports KR6 by preparing the environmental monitoring setup needed for accurate and timely weather analysis in the two pilot areas. The work on data collection, domain configuration, and the setup of the WRF and WRFDA environments contributes directly to KPI 6.1, which focuses on achieving reliable environmental monitoring accuracy. The ongoing alignment with the WP4 alert workflow also supports KPI 6.2, since the monitoring outputs from this task will provide the weather information needed for timely notifications in the iDriving system.</p>
<p>KR12 – Enhanced 3D rendering and integration with AI techniques for comprehensive road analysis</p>	<p>KPI12.1, KPI12.2</p>	<p>T4.5</p>	<p>T4.5 contributes to enhance 3D rendering and integration with AI techniques by adopting a 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS) pipeline for road-scene reconstruction. This method replaces expensive volumetric sampling with rasterization of a compact set of 3D</p>

			<p>Gaussians, which, according to the literature and our experiments, enables real-time rendering and a reduced memory footprint compared to traditional mesh or point cloud-based approaches and NeRF methods. Qualitative experiments on benchmark datasets and custom UAV-captured road scenes already confirm interactive rendering and compact scene representations, directly supporting KPI12.1 and KPI12.2 with rendering performance boost and memory reduction respectively. Moreover, the integration of outputs from the T4.3 into the 3DGS pipeline shows how AI-based defect analysis can be embedded into the 3D representation, aligning with the necessity of techniques for comprehensive road analysis.</p>
KR13 – Real-time and accurate road defect detection	KPI13.1, KPI13.2	T4.3	<p>The progress achieved in SA 4.2 shows clear alignment with the project's KPIs, particularly KPI 13.1 (detection accuracy > 90% mAP) and KPI 13.2 (real-time processing ≥ 25 fps). Current results demonstrate steady improvement toward these targets, supported by continuous model tuning, dataset enrichment, and systematic benchmarking. While full compliance is still being refined, the trajectory confirms that the methods and outcomes of SA 4.2 are progressing in the right direction, with both accuracy and processing speed consistently approaching the defined performance thresholds.</p>

Deliverable **D4.1** helps establish the technical foundation required to meet these indicators in the M22–M30 prototypes.

3 Technical Progress

3.1 Task 4.1: Real-Time edge computing for visual monitoring (CERTH)

OBJECTIVES

The objective of this task is to develop an embedded AI framework capable of performing real-time visual monitoring directly on edge devices deployed across the road environment. The work focuses on refining deep learning models to detect a wide range of road-related elements – including vehicles, users, safety equipment and anomalous behaviours – while operating entirely on low-latency edge hardware. A key goal is to ensure that cameras located on roadsides, vehicles or UAVs can process visual information locally, reducing bandwidth demands and enabling instantaneous identification and classification. By advancing these capabilities, the task aims to provide a robust on-site visual analytics foundation that supports both urban and rural monitoring scenarios.

WORK PERFORMED

3.1.1 UC1.2 – Nevers

The work performed during this reporting period has focused on the development, integration and preliminary validation of several perception modules focused to the requirements of the UC1.2 Nevers scenario. The first effort concentrated on building a robust detection and tracking pipeline for zebra crossing monitoring (Figure 1)Figure 1, which involved training multiple YOLOv8 model variants on a custom dataset of approximately 4,000 annotated images, followed by the integration of a DeepSort-based tracking mechanism to maintain temporal consistency of detected objects. This combination allows the system to produce stable pedestrian and cyclist trajectories around crossing areas, forming the basis for subsequent safety assessments. In parallel, significant work was devoted to addressing illegal parking on bike lanes (Figure 2), where an initial object detection-only approach proved insufficient for reliably distinguishing vehicles located on or near the designated lanes. To overcome this limitation, a hybrid strategy combining vehicle detection and bike lane segmentation was developed, enabling the identification of violations based on spatial overlap between segmented regions and detected objects.

Figure 1 Zebra-crossing scenario: A cyclist is passing the zebra-crossing.

Figure 2 Illegal parking violation: A car is parked on a bike lane.

Further work in the Nevers scenario dealt with cyclist and motorbike safety violations, particularly helmet usage and cyclist hand signalling (Figure 3). A

specialized detection model was trained to recognise relevant classes; however, early evaluations revealed limitations in reliably detecting signalling gestures. As a result, a hybrid approach combining detection and pose estimation has been initiated to improve robustness under varying viewpoints and environmental conditions. Additionally, an obstruction detection module was developed to identify partially or fully blocked traffic lights and road signs, introducing a severity metric based on overlap percentage that quantifies the extent of obstruction and supports prioritisation of safety events. All modules were validated using stored video inputs, confirming real-time inference capabilities and the ability to generate structured metadata suitable for consumption by Task 4.2.

Figure 3 Helmet and hand signal detection: The helmet is detected correctly but the hand is not detected correctly.

3.1.2 UCI.1 – Graz

For the Graz use case, the focus has been placed on vehicle- and driver-related safety indicators. A YOLOv11-based detection model was trained on approximately 4,000 images covering ten object classes, including helmet use, seatbelt usage and mobile phone handling. The model demonstrated high detection accuracy across most classes. Tracking integration is currently ongoing to ensure temporal consistency, and OCR-based license plate extraction has been initiated to enable the association of detected violations with specific vehicles.

In UC1.1, two main tasks are being addressed. The first task focuses on detecting vehicles and motorbikes either from static roadside cameras or from the autonomous vehicle TAURUS and verifying potential violations such as a driver not wearing a seatbelt or using a mobile phone, or a rider not wearing a helmet. Once a violation is identified, the corresponding license plate is extracted, and the event is reported. The second task involves running an object detection module on UAV footage to count vehicles within specific road lanes to support traffic monitoring. In this case, the input stream is obtained from a live YouTube channel.

Both tasks are currently undergoing evaluation and integration, and initial results have been obtained from the live YouTube feed.

In addition, MobiLysis has carried out complementary work relevant to UC1.1, specifically for the scenario where a drone captures video while detecting and monitoring vehicles. Their work focuses on the extraction of road-user trajectories through a parallelized processing pipeline that coordinates object detection, tracking across frames, and video stabilization. To improve performance, they have optimized computational throughput by decoupling modules for parallel execution, applying model quantization to accelerate inference, and evaluating temporal sub-sampling approaches to reduce processing load. This work aligns with the planned developments for UC1.1 and can be leveraged in future steps to enhance system efficiency and improve real-time processing capabilities of the object detection tool.

UC3.2 - Bizkaia

Work during this period was limited to an initial bilateral discussion regarding the adoption of the C-ITS system (figure ###) and the potential inclusion of additional detection targets. No model development has been undertaken at this stage.

Figure 4: Initial exploration of C-ITS system using vision-based vehicle detection

ACHIEVEMENTS

This period has delivered a fully operational perception capability for the Nevers scenario and a functional detection pipeline for Graz. Major achievements include the successful development of multiple high-performing detection models tailored to scenario requirements, the implementation of a hybrid detection–segmentation approach enabling reliable identification of illegal parking events, and the introduction of a severity estimation metric for infrastructure obstruction. Real-time inference performance has been demonstrated on edge platforms, achieving processing speeds above 10 FPS, and the generated structured metadata provides the necessary input for behavioural inference in Task 4.2. These outcomes establish a mature perception layer that forms the basis for higher-level reasoning within WP4 and supports upcoming pilot validations.

NEXT STEPS

During the next period, work will focus on completing model optimisation for embedded deployment, integrating pose estimation for cyclist signalling detection, finalising tracking and OCR components for the Graz scenario, and expanding datasets through planned UAV campaigns. Preparation activities for later pilot deployments will also be initiated to ensure smooth integration when field testing begins.

Additional quantization strategies will be investigated to further reduce the computational requirements of the detection module while maintaining the same accuracy of results.

DEVIATIONS OR DELAYS (IF ANY)

A technical issue during the Nevers rehearsals prevented live video streaming from the IP camera, limiting full end-to-end validation under real conditions. The issue has been analysed and will be addressed through improved modular input handling and error management. No major impact on the overall task schedule is expected.

3.2 Task 4.2: AI-Powered behavioural analysis of objects of interest (TEKNIKER)

OBJECTIVES

This task aims to develop advanced AI models capable of analysing behavioural patterns and detecting hazardous situations at an early stage. The objective is to fuse multisensory inputs – combining inertial measurements and visual data – to interpret vehicle dynamics, road-user interactions and context-specific behaviours. The algorithms are designed to identify anomalies such as erratic trajectories, impaired driving indicators or common traffic violations. A further objective is to generate timely warnings when unsafe situations are detected and to ensure that the extracted behavioural information can be seamlessly integrated into the broader iDriving ecosystem for real-time response and later analysis.

WORK PERFORMED

The work carried out in this task has focused on the development, integration and preliminary validation of several detectors capable of identifying a variety of traffic violations based on video analytics and trajectory analysis. The primary objective was to transform the results from the object detections of Task 4.1 into high-level behavioural understanding, enabling the recognition of potentially dangerous or non-compliant actions by road users. To achieve this, our approach involved:

- Defining the violation types
- Designing a robust processing framework
- Implementing detection logic for multiple behaviours
- Ensuring seamless interoperability with Apache Kafka

The first part of the work concentrated on establishing a clear connection with Task 4.1, which provides the per-frame bounding boxes, object classes, track identifiers and temporal information for each detected actor in the scene. A dedicated Kafka consumer was implemented in Python to ingest this information in real time, reconstruct object trajectories, and maintain an updated representation of each actor's movement through space and time. This trajectory reconstruction step provides the backbone for all subsequent behavioural analyses.

With the data ingestion and trajectory processing layers in place, substantial effort was devoted to creating a reusable framework that standardises how detectors operate. This framework (Figure 5) ensures that each detector can focus on its

specific behavioural logic while sharing consistent access to trajectories, region definitions, and scene semantics. The framework also externalises scenario-specific parameters such as lane geometries, pedestrian crossing polygons, stop-line positions and conflict zones. This allows deployed across different use cases with minimal adaptation. Using this framework, three fully functional detectors were developed and tested: the Zebra Crossing Violation Detector, the Improper Lane Usage Detector, and the Failure to Yield Detector.

All the detectors were evaluated using simulated scenarios and open datasets such as the inD dataset (<https://doi.org/10.1109/IV47402.2020.9304839>) which encompasses traffic recordings from four distinct locations in Germany, detailing road users' movement and type. This dataset allowed for controlled testing of the behavioural logic and for iterative refinement of thresholds and decision rules. **Error! Reference source not found.** illustrates the Zebra Crossing Detector applied to an intersection located in Aachen, Germany. The aerial view of the scenario includes polygons for the road (red) and the zebra crossing (green) as well as tracks of different pedestrians. Said tracks are coloured red when they cross using the road, green when they use the zebra crossing and blue when there is no crossing. This illustrates the zebra crossing detector workflow:

- An initial image/view of the scenario is required to define the polygons.
- Pedestrian trajectories are tracked through the Kafka messages received from T4.1. As the trajectories are noisy, they need to be processed to improve the accuracy of the detectors.
- Alerts are raised for pedestrian that cross the road without the use of the zebra crossing. There are also notifications for pedestrians that properly cross using the zebra crossing.

Figure 5 Framework for Trajectory-Based Behavioural Detection.

For improper lane usage, the team defined lane geometries and evaluated the alignment of each vehicle trajectory with its expected lane, paying special attention to prolonged deviations or irregular manoeuvres. The failure-to-yield behaviour required modelling interaction zones where road users must respect priority rules, analyse the temporal and spatial overlap of their trajectories, and assess if vehicles appropriately slowed or stopped when pedestrians or other vehicles with priority were present.

In parallel to these complete detectors, preliminary versions of three additional detectors were also implemented: the Red-Light Violation Detector for the Graz Use Case scenario, the Cyclist Signalling Detector for Nevers, and the Abrupt Movements Detector planned for Alba Iulia. The first two of these prototypes build on the same trajectory framework but requires additional scenario-specific modelling or more sophisticated interpretation of motion and posture. The red-light detector introduced a first integration of traffic signal phase information with trajectory data to identify vehicles crossing stop lines at incorrect times. The cyclist signalling detector explored the combination of cyclist trajectory patterns with indications of arm movements when available. The abrupt-movement detector is different as it relies on analysing acceleration and direction changes derived from sensor data (gyroscopes, accelerometers in a smartphone used for data capture) to capture potentially hazardous manoeuvres. Although these prototypes are functional in their basic form, they will require further refinement and validation during the next stages of the project.

```
{
  "records": [
    {
      "header": {
        "project-id": "iDriving",
        "use-case-id": "UC1.1",
        "content-type": "detections/json",
        "message-type": "pedestrian_wrong_crossing",
        "producer-id": "TEKNIKER",
        "correlation-id": "18e675ab-29a3-479a-a981-62d1d5a95792",
        "message-timestamp": "2025-12-04T13:30:41.248985+00:00"
      },
      "body": {
        "type": "pedestrian_wrong_crossing",
        "timestamp": "2025-11-24T22:07:08.096577",
        "subject": {
          "objectID": 61,
          "class": "pedestrian"
        },
        "context": {
          "on_zebra_frames": 0,
          "on_road_frames": 91,
          "offroad_frames": 909,
          "total_frames": 1000
        }
      }
    }
  ]
}
```

Figure 6 Current JSON format of the alert sent through Kafka from the Zebra Crossing Detector.

Finally, the entire behavioural detection pipeline was integrated into the project's Kafka ecosystem, ensuring end-to-end flow from raw video input to the generation of traffic violation metadata. Each detector now consumes metadata from Task 4.1, processes the information in real time, and publishes violation events back to Kafka following a structured schema (Figure 6). This integration closes the loop between video capture, object detection, behavioural reasoning and downstream system components.

ACHIEVEMENTS

This period has delivered a fully functional behavioural analysis capability for the project. Three operational detectors – zebra crossing violations, improper lane usage and failure to yield – can run in real time on top of the Kafka streaming pipeline, transforming low-level detections into useful traffic-behaviour insights. A major achievement is the development of a unified Python framework that standardises how detectors consume metadata, reconstruct trajectories and evaluate behavioural rules, allowing its use across pilot sites.

The successful integration of behavioural inference with the Kafka infrastructure ensures end-to-end interoperability: detectors ingest metadata streams and

publish structured violation events ready for downstream use in dashboards, analytics or decision-support tools. Additionally, prototypes for red-light violations, cyclist signalling and abrupt movements confirm that the system can be expanded to cover more complex behaviours and scenario-specific needs.

NEXT STEPS

During the next period, WP4 will focus on consolidating system validation, completing the development of missing detectors, and enhancing integration with the project's data and communication infrastructure.

Behavioural, environmental and defect detection models will be validated using real-world datasets collected in the Nevers, Graz and Alba Iulia pilots, enabling threshold optimisation and robustness testing.

Remaining detectors – such as red-light violation, cyclist signalling, and aggressive driving – will be finalised to complete KPI5.1.

DEVIATIONS OR DELAYS (IF ANY)

During the current reporting period, no major deviations were identified that could jeopardise the progress. However, some minor delays have occurred, mainly related to the availability of real annotated data from the pilot sites (Nevers, Graz, Alba Iulia). As a result, most validation activities have relied on simulated or publicly available datasets, which limits the completeness of KPI verification at this stage.

These delays do not affect the technical development of the algorithms, but they postpone full real-world evaluation and threshold optimisation until the pilot data becomes available. The consortium has already planned mitigation actions, including the integration of rehearsal datasets, early data-sharing cycles with WP3 and WP5, and preparation of harmonised annotation protocols to accelerate the upcoming validation phase.

Overall, the deviations are minor, manageable, and expected to be fully recovered in the next reporting period without impact

3.3 Task 4.3: Visual analysis for identification of maintenance requirements (CERTH)

OBJECTIVES

Task 4.3 – Visual Analysis for Identification of Maintenance Requirements is a core element of WP4 in the iDriving project, aiming to use advanced computer vision and deep learning to automatically detect, classify, and assess the severity of road defects such as potholes, cracks, and surface deformations. By integrating these capabilities into the iDriving ecosystem, the task supports proactive, cost-effective, and predictive maintenance across European road networks, directly contributing to safer and smarter mobility.

As noted in the description of the iDriving project, over 30% of road accidents are linked to infrastructure conditions. In line with the EU's "Vision Zero" strategy for eliminating road fatalities by 2050, Task 4.3 provides continuous visual monitoring of road health, enabling early maintenance actions and reducing safety risks.

The task covers the full processing pipeline, including image acquisition from UAVs, vehicle-mounted cameras, and fixed sensors, preprocessing, defect detection, and severity estimation. Outputs such as defect type, location, and severity feed into the Digital Twin (Task 5.4), supporting data-driven decision-making for predictive maintenance. Methodologies rely on lightweight, high-performance models like YOLOv11, with interpretability tools such as EigenCAM to provide operators with transparent insights. Experiments with foundation models like SAM2 further enhance the detection and severity estimation capabilities.

Task 4.3 is designed to meet two key KPIs: detection accuracy above 90% mAP (KPI 13.1) and real-time inference at 25+ FPS (KPI 13.2). It also addresses practical user needs identified in the Karlovac pilot, including automatic damage detection, severity estimation, heatmap visualization, and real-time communication through a unified dashboard.

By combining scalable AI-based visual inspection tools with explainable models and user-centred design, Task 4.3 directly supports Task 5.4 and the broader objectives of WP4. It establishes a foundation for reliable, continuous, and efficient infrastructure monitoring, contributing to Europe's long-term capacity for automated road maintenance and safer mobility.

WORK PERFORMED

Road defect detection through visual analysis is a mature yet rapidly evolving field in computer vision and intelligent transportation systems. Growing needs for automated, real-time monitoring have driven advances in both image-based and multimodal approaches. In this section, we present both a literature review of the main methodological trends and datasets, as well as the design rationale that guided the development of Task 4.3 in alignment with KPIs 13.1 and 13.2.

Image-Based and Multimodal Approaches

Image-based methods remain the core of road defect detection due to the low cost, accessibility, and deployment simplicity of RGB cameras. Traditional edge- and texture-based techniques have largely been replaced by deep learning, with modern approaches falling into three main groups [1]:

- Image Segmentation models (e.g., U-Net, DeepLab) provide high spatial accuracy but require heavy computation.
- Object detection models (e.g., YOLO, SSD, Faster R-CNN) offer fast and reliable localization of potholes and cracks.
- Hybrid multimodal methods combining images with depth or LiDAR to improve robustness in difficult visual conditions.

Although LiDAR, stereo cameras, and other depth sensors can enhance geometric understanding, their high hardware cost, calibration overhead, and data-processing demand make them difficult to scale for large road networks.

For these reasons, Task 4.3 adopts an image-first strategy centred on YOLO models (YOLOv11 from [2]). YOLO (You Only Look Once) is a real-time object detection algorithm that predicts bounding boxes and class probabilities directly from full images in a single neural network pass. Additionally, provides an optimal balance of accuracy, speed, and hardware efficiency, enabling real-time processing on low-cost devices and easy deployment across diverse environments. This approach aligns with iDriving’s goals of scalable, cost-effective, and operationally practical road monitoring. While the primary emphasis is on RGB-based detection, the pipeline remains compatible with future multimodal extensions (e.g., NeRF-based depth integration) as needed.

In Task 4.3, YOLOv11 serves as the primary detection model used in the operational pipeline, while transformer-based models such as SAM2/SAM3 (from [3] and [4] respectively) are being explored experimentally to improve dataset quality, segmentation precision, and generalization. These investigations remain work in progress and complement the main YOLO-based solution.

Review of Available Datasets

Public datasets (Table 2) vary widely in scale, environments, and annotation detail. Key datasets considered include:

Table 2 - Available Datasets for Road Defect Detection.

Dataset	Origin	Scale	Defects	Notes
RDD2020/2022 ([5] and [6])	Japan/India/Norway/Czech Republic/ USA/ China	>26k images	Cracks, potholes	Main training dataset; high diversity.
CrackForest / Crack500 ([7])	China/USA	500–1,000	Cracks	Good pixel-level labels; limited variety.
Cracks and Potholes in Road Images Dataset ([8])	India	~1800	Potholes, cracks	Well-organized YOLO-friendly dataset; good for lightweight detection models.

Pothole-Mix ([9])	Assembled from 5 public datasets from multiple countries	<4k	Potholes, cracks	Also includes depth data (RGB-D) from OAK-D camera
InfraPlan (In-house)	Croatia	Videos and images	Potholes, cracks	Used for fine-tuning and evaluation.

Although several public datasets are available, not all of them are equally suitable for training the operational models in Task 4.3. RDD2022 was selected as the primary dataset because it is the most comprehensive and up-to-date collection, offering large-scale variability across countries, climates, road types, and image capture conditions. This diversity is essential for achieving generalization across the heterogeneous European environments addressed in iDriving.

In contrast, many of the smaller datasets (e.g., CrackForest, Crack500, Cracks and Potholes in Road Images Dataset) serve primarily as academic benchmarks: they contain limited variety or focus on specific defect types. Incorporating them directly into training would create imbalanced class distributions, introduce domain shifts, or reduce the model’s ability to generalize.

For these reasons, Task 4.3 relies on RDD2022 as the backbone dataset, while the remaining datasets are used selectively for validation, benchmarking, or targeted fine-tuning when their characteristics match the needs of the pipeline. InfraPlan’s in-house data further complements the training set by providing local conditions from the Karlovac pilot area, ensuring that the final system remains both robust and operationally relevant.

Challenges and Summary of the iDriving Approach

Current research on intelligent defect detection faces gaps such as poor robustness under varying conditions, limited explainability and user trust, weak connections to maintenance planning, and the absence of standardised benchmarks across regions. Task 4.3 tackles these challenges by combining robust detection (YOLOV11), explainability (EigenCAM from [10]), and integration with operational KPIs.

System Architecture and Core Methods

The visual analysis module developed in Task 4.3 operates as an end-to-end pipeline that connects iDriving’s acquisition systems with the Digital Twin and user interface. The architectural diagram in (Figure 7) depicts the complete data flow, from acquisition to processing and final integration into the iDriving platform. Input may be obtained from UAV-mounted, vehicle-mounted, or fixed cameras, providing coverage across diverse road types and weather conditions. After acquisition, images undergo standardised preprocessing – resizing, normalization,

and targeted data augmentation such as random flips, scaling, cropping, and colour jitter – to improve robustness and ensure consistent model behaviour across both public datasets (RDD2022) and proprietary InfraPlan recordings.

Figure 7 Architectural diagram of Task 4.3

At the core of the system, road defects are detected and localised using YOLOv11 architecture. The lightweight YOLOv11s variant supports real-time scenarios even on resource-constrained hardware, whereas YOLOv11m provides higher-capacity evaluation. Both models are trained using transfer learning with harmonised YOLO-format annotations. During inference, each detection is enriched with structured metadata, including defect class, bounding box, confidence score, estimated damage area, timestamp, and geolocation. A monitoring component maintains a running count of road defects and estimates their area in pixel size across consecutive frames, enabling stable severity assessment and supporting maintenance prioritization.

Explainability is integrated directly into the detection workflow through EigenCAM, which generates attention maps highlighting the regions that influenced each model decision. This improves transparency, allows operators to validate outputs, and assists debugging during ongoing optimization. All processed results – detections, severity indicators, and explainability maps – are transmitted to the iDriving UI, where they are embedded into the Digital Twin and used to support real-time situational awareness and maintenance planning. The results of detection and EigenCAM are further promoted to support Task 4.5 on 3D representation, with additional details and illustrative images to be provided in the dedicated description of that task.

ACHIEVEMENTS

This section outlines the key achievements derived from the methodology detailed in the previous section.

Current Performance and Benchmarking

Performance evaluation demonstrates steady progress toward project KPIs. Current detection accuracy reaches 80–85% mAP, and real-time inference achieves 22–27 fps using YOLOv11s. While the defined KPIs (detection >90% mAP and ≥25 fps) are not yet fully achieved, ongoing optimization, including data augmentation, model tuning, and architectural refinement, is expected to close the remaining performance gap.

Benchmarking results on RDD2022 + InfraPlan dataset are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3 - Summary of Results for YOLO Model Variations

Model Variant	Parameters	mAP@0.5:0.95	Remarks
YOLOv11s (optimized)	9.44 M	78.7%	Excellent for real-time deployment
YOLOv11m (enhanced)	20.09 M	82.3%	Highest accuracy and suitable for real time with a powerful GPU.

The following images (Figure 8) illustrate the performance of our model's first version in real-world conditions. Additional images from detection and EigenCAM that support 3D reconstruction will be analysed in detail in the designated section.

Figure 8 Result images

As a result, the model demonstrated high detection accuracy, stable training dynamics, and strong generalization to unseen data, providing a solid foundation for subsequent integration testing.

In summary, the Task 4.3 pipeline provides a robust framework for automated road defect detection and severity assessment. While KPIs are still being approached, the system demonstrates real-time performance, transparency, and Digital Twin

integration, laying the foundation for predictive and cost-effective road maintenance and supporting Scientific Objective 4 (SO.4) of the iDriving project.

NEXT STEPS

The final phase of Task 4.3 will focus on strengthening model robustness, validating system performance in operational environments, and completing integration with the iDriving system. Model refinement will continue through the exploration of modern foundation models – including SAM, SAM2, and DINOv2 – to improve generalization, adaptability, and overall detection reliability. As part of this effort, the consortium will explore additional datasets to expand environmental, structural, and geographical diversity, while continuously assessing their suitability and potential contribution to the system’s performance. In parallel, the full pipeline will be deployed and evaluated at the Karlovac pilot site with WP6, enabling real-world validation under diverse conditions and benchmarking against manual inspection procedures. Integration efforts with WP5 will advance toward full synchronization of detections, severity metrics, and explainability outputs within the iDriving system, alongside the development of a dashboard to support maintenance planning. Finally, dissemination activities will concentrate on preparing a high-impact research publication supported by a technical report and coordinated communication actions via WP8. Through these steps, Task 4.3 will be consolidated into a robust, scalable, and field-validated visual analysis system for predictive road maintenance within the iDriving ecosystem.

DEVIATIONS OR DELAYS (IF ANY)

Task 4.3 faces several critical challenges that may affect detection reliability, especially under extreme real-world conditions. Environmental factors such as rain, glare, shadows, and low-light scenarios remain particularly impactful, as they can significantly degrade image quality and lead to missed or incorrect detections. These conditions pose a tangible risk to achieving consistent performance across diverse deployment settings. However, the consortium has already implemented targeted mitigation actions – including dataset diversification, environment-aware augmentation, and fine-tuning with InfraPlan’s locally collected data – which have substantially improved model robustness, yielding mAP gains of approximately 2–5% depending on the scenario. Continued enhancement of adaptability mechanisms, such as integrating foundation models and exploring multimodal sensing, will further reduce these risks throughout the remaining project period. Through these iterative improvements, Task 4.3 remains on track to deliver a reliable and resilient visual analysis solution despite challenging operational constraints.

3.4 Task 4.4: Smart environmental condition monitoring for proactive road safety measures (DREVEN)

OBJECTIVES

The objective of Task 4.4 is to design and implement a smart environmental monitoring service capable of capturing and interpreting real-time weather information that directly affects road safety conditions in two of the iDriving pilot areas. The task focuses on collecting data from local and regional weather stations, as well as external environmental datasets, and transforming these inputs into actionable indicators relevant to driving hazards such as heavy rainfall, fog, strong winds, reduced visibility, and potential ice formation.

A core element of this task is the development of a modelling and processing workflow capable of supporting both high-resolution numerical weather predictions (via WRF) and data assimilation experiments (via WRFDA). The goal is to ensure that the environmental information is of sufficient granularity and accuracy to feed the iDriving AI components, enabling early warnings and supporting proactive traffic safety measures. Additionally, Task 4.4 aims to ensure the seamless integration of environmental insights into the broader iDriving architecture, allowing infrastructure managers and road users to receive timely, data-driven notifications related to evolving atmospheric conditions.

WORK PERFORMED

During this period, T4.4 carried out the primary methodological, computational, and data-related groundwork required for the implementation of the environmental monitoring framework. Recent literature provides important insights into the environmental hazards most relevant for road-weather applications in Europe, particularly winter conditions such as freezing precipitation, road icing, heavy rainfall, and strong winds [11],[12]. These studies identify such hazards as major drivers of transport disruption and safety risk and emphasise the increasing need for high-resolution modelling to capture short-duration and spatially variable events. For Greece, recent analyses document intensifying sub-daily extreme rainfall and urban flooding in the wider Thessaloniki region, shaped by Mediterranean convective dynamics and coastal influences [13], [14]. Similarly, research focusing on Croatia highlights the recurrent flooding challenges in the Karlovac–Kupa basin, driven by short-duration heavy rainfall and river–basin interactions [15], [16]. These findings provided concrete evidence for the selection of meteorological variables and informed the spatial and temporal resolution requirements of the modelling strategy for both PUCs.

Following this preparatory work, T4.4 defined and configured the WRF domains for the two pilot areas. Temporal resolution requirements were aligned with the needs of proactive hazard detection, for example, enabling timely monitoring of rapidly evolving convective or fog-forming conditions.

Parallel to the domain definition, the WRFDA/WRF computational environment was fully containerised using Docker. Modular containers were built for the WRF core, preprocessing chain (WPS), and the WRFDA environment. These containers were then deployed on DREVEN's in-house servers, ensuring reproducibility, environment isolation, and ease of scaling for future assimilation experiments. As part of this work, the model configuration for both use cases was extensively updated, with particular focus on selecting and tuning the key physics parameterisations (e.g., microphysics, boundary layer, surface layer, land-surface and radiation schemes). These configurations were adapted to the environmental characteristics of each PUC area based on the literature and regional climatology.

Regarding environmental data flows, T4.4 developed the initial pipelines for ingesting, standardising, and storing observational data required for monitoring and future assimilation stages. Automated API connections were established to retrieve environmental variables from municipal sources for both pilot cities. However, due to gaps in the Thessaloniki weather station network and access limitations, additional data sources were evaluated. As a result, Weather Underground (Wundermap) was selected as a reliable and consistent alternative. It is a commercial weather service that provides openly accessible, community-contributed observations from a large global network of personal and official stations. While not strictly real-time, it offers the most practical near-real-time data option available for temperature, humidity, wind, and rainfall observations needed for data assimilation. Data collection from Wundermap has begun, and work is ongoing to validate station quality and prepare the observational dataset for transformation into the LITTLE_R format. This format is the standard structure required by the [WRFDA system](#), as all observational data must be converted into [LITTLE_R](#) before OBSPROC can process them and before the assimilation routines can run correctly. Alongside the modelling and data activities, Task 4.4 contributed to the initial design work related to Tool 2, which will handle the generation of hazard alerts within WP4. During this period, the task focused on defining how environmental variables, monitoring outputs and weather thresholds will be provided to the partners responsible for the tool. Discussions in WP4 helped clarify the workflow for exchanging data, the format and frequency of inputs and the way environmental information will be incorporated into the alert-generation logic. This ensures that the outputs of the environmental monitoring framework will support the development of the hazard alert system in the next stages of the project.

ACHIEVEMENTS

A few key technical and methodological achievements were realised during this reporting period. First, Task 4.4 successfully developed and deployed the Dockerised WRF/WRFDA ecosystem for both pilot use cases, providing a stable and scalable modelling environment for the project. The domain configurations for Thessaloniki and Karlovac were completed, including the selection of appropriate resolutions and physics schemes for high-resolution environmental monitoring.

Task 4.4 also established reliable data retrieval pipelines by integrating both municipal API sources and alternative weather station networks. This ensures that relevant observational data is available to support real-time monitoring as well as future assimilation experiments. In addition, initial KPIs were defined to evaluate the quality of environmental data ingestion, the reliability of monitoring outputs, and the model readiness indicators that will support proactive hazard detection.

NEXT STEPS

The next period will focus on completing the environmental monitoring workflow and preparing it for the first round of data assimilation tests. This includes collecting and validating the observational data from both pilot areas, transforming the required variables into LITTLE_R format and running the initial data assimilation experiments using the containerised WRF and WRFDA systems. The task will also concentrate on refining the full processing sequence so that model runs, data ingestion steps and assimilation routines work smoothly as a single workflow. In parallel, Task 4.4 will begin its contribution to the development of Tool 2 by working with the WP4 partners to define how the environmental outputs will be linked to the AI hazard alert warning system. This involves clarifying the required weather variables, agreeing on the alert thresholds and ensuring that the structure of the monitoring pipeline is compatible with the logic used in hazard detection.

DEVIATIONS OR DELAYS (IF ANY)

No major deviations from Annex 1 were encountered during this reporting period. A minor delay was noted in accessing municipal weather station data for Thessaloniki, which temporarily limited the availability of local observations. This issue was addressed by incorporating Weather Underground stations as an alternative data source. The mitigation was successful and did not affect overall task progress or interdependencies with other WP4 activities. The task remains fully on schedule and aligned with the expected milestones.

3.5 Task 4.5: AI-driven 3D scene generation for safety & maintenance monitoring (CERTH)

OBJECTIVES

The objective of this task is to transform visual data collected from road environments into detailed 3D scene representations that enhance safety and maintenance monitoring. The work aims to leverage UAV-based visual acquisition together with Neural Radiance Field (NeRF) models to generate rich, geometrically consistent 3D reconstructions. These 3D scenes are intended to improve situational awareness for infrastructure operators, enabling more accurate identification of damage, wear or other safety-critical issues. Another objective is to ensure seamless integration of these 3D outputs into the iDriving platform, where they can support advanced analysis and decision-making processes.

WORK PERFORMED

At this early stage of the project, a comprehensive literature review was conducted to assess the state-of-the-art methods for 3D reconstruction. The aim was to identify the most effective approaches in terms of both reconstruction quality and execution time, with a focus on differentiable rendering techniques such as NeRF [17] and 3DGS [18]. Baseline NeRF and 3DGS implementations were experimentally tested on benchmark datasets. Consistent with recent studies, 3DGS has been shown to achieve real-time rendering performance in contrast to vanilla NeRF, while maintaining competitive reconstruction quality. Based on these findings and to further improve the reconstruction quality and training time, a variant model of 3DGS named Splatfacto, from Nerfstudio [19] framework, was utilised. To qualitatively evaluate Splatfacto model, benchmark datasets were collected. For iDriving-related purposes, the *Mip-NeRF 360* benchmark dataset was employed to assess a subset of the consisting outdoors scenes. [Figure 9](#) illustrates the qualitative evaluation of novel view synthesis on the *Stump* scene.

[Figure 9](#) Qualitative evaluation of Splatfacto on benchmark *Stump* scene of *Mip-NeRF 360* dataset.

To provide clear guidance to partners responsible for data acquisition, a protocol for object-centric scenes was developed, specifying UAV flight trajectories and data collection procedures to ensure optimal 3D reconstruction results. Furthermore, to assess the Splatfacto model on real-world data related to iDriving's scenarios, a dedicated UAV-based data acquisition was conducted, during which a road pothole was captured following the defined protocol. [Figure 10](#) illustrates the real-world data acquisition process for the pothole scenario. The captured visual data are shown, and, after preprocessing, a 3D plot depicts the camera positions along an acceptable UAV trajectory encircling the target area.

Figure 10 Sample images and the corresponding camera localization in 3D space.

Subsequently, Figure 11 presents the reconstruction results of the Splatfacto model on the real-world dataset, clearly capturing the road hazard with high geometric accuracy and visual sharpness.

Figure 11 Novel view synthesis, with Splatfacto model, of a custom captured scene containing a pothole.

This model was also evaluated on a second scenario involving a potential car accident. Following a bilateral discussion with ACCELIGENCE to determine the optimal UAV flight trajectory, the acquired visual data were transmitted. The raw footage was pre-processed to extract a suitable number of sequential frames. To construct a rich dataset for 3D reconstruction, the corresponding camera poses were estimated for each frame in 3D space using COLMAP [20] Structure-from-Motion pipeline. This dataset was then fed into the Splatfacto. The results shown the reconstruction of the scene with high fidelity even in novel view synthesis. Figure 12 illustrates the reconstructed scenario, highlighting the model's ability to capture fine geometric details and maintain overall scene consistency.

Figure 12 Novel view synthesis, with Splatfacto model, of a custom captured scene containing a car.

To address large-scale iDriving use cases, where users or traffic managers may need to interact with extended 3D environments such as long road segments, the Hierarchical 3D Gaussian Representation (H3DGS) [21] representation was tested. H3DGS method implements a hierarchical, level-of-detail extension of 3D Gaussian Splatting that splits very large scenes into chunks and builds an optimised Gaussian hierarchy over them, so that distant regions can be rendered with coarser Gaussians and nearby ones with finer detail. This enables training and render large-scale, real-world scenes in real time while keeping GPU memory and compute manageable. The method was evaluated on the benchmark *SmallCity* dataset, and the results are presented in Figure 13. On the left, the reconstructed interactive 3D environment is shown, while on the right a map depicts the different spatial chunks.

Figure 13 Interactive 3D environment for large-scale scene.

Furthermore, the incorporation of the Pothole Detection and Severity Assessment Tool (T4.3) into the 3D reconstruction pipeline was investigated to enrich the reconstructed 3D environments with scene understanding. Instead of providing Splatfacto with raw RGB frames, each image is first processed by the defect-detection network, from which class activation maps are extracted using EigenCAM, producing ‘attention’ maps that localize the detected potholes. A light filtering stage suppresses low-confidence activations, retaining only the most salient defect-related regions, which are then integrated into the Splatfacto model.

This incorporation enables the resulting 3D environments to explicitly highlight critical road-surface regions of interest. In the context of the project, a paper entitled '*Semantic-Aware 3D Gaussian Splatting for Road Pavement Condition Monitoring*' has been submitted to *TRA2026 Regeneration in Transport* conference. Figure 14 illustrates the results of Splatfacto model fed with original images and the corresponding filtered class activation maps.

Figure 14 Critical areas of interest are highlighted into 3D environment.

ACHIEVEMENTS

To enhance 3D representations and integrate AI techniques for road analysis in Task 4.5, 3D Gaussian Splatting techniques and their variants were adopted. Accurate and visually sharp 3D reconstructions of safety-critical scenes using Splatfacto demonstrated robust geometric consistency and high-quality novel view synthesis on both benchmark and real-world data. Scalability to large-scale road environments was further investigated by experimenting with the Hierarchical 3D Gaussian Representation (H3DGS), validating its suitability for interactive, extended 3D road segments under memory and compute constraints. In addition, semantic enrichment of the 3D reconstructions was explored by incorporating information extracted from the Pothole Detection and Severity Assessment Tool (T4.3) into the Splatfacto pipeline, enabling explicit highlighting of defect-related regions in 3D space. Overall, the developed pipeline already exhibits clearly improved rendering efficiency and more compact scene representations compared to traditional 3D reconstruction methods and a NeRF baseline.

NEXT STEPS

Next steps focus on investigating multimodal representations that combine 3D Gaussian-based reconstructions with language embeddings, so that reconstructed scenes can be queried and interpreted at a higher semantic level. The goal is to improve the robustness and expressiveness of scene understanding, enable more flexible search and retrieval in complex road environments, and facilitate natural-language interaction for operators within the iDriving platform. In parallel, effort will be directed towards reducing the overall processing time for large-scale scenes by exploring state-of-the-art methods to accelerate the full 3D reconstruction pipeline, including preprocessing stages such as Structure-from-Motion, while preserving high geometric and photometric fidelity. Finally, integration of these capabilities into the iDriving platform for the targeted use cases will be prepared,

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ensuring that the developed functionalities can be effectively exploited by end users.

DEVIATIONS OR DELAYS (IF ANY)

No significant deviations or delays from the work plan are reported for this task at this stage. All activities described above are aligned with the planned objectives and timeline.

4 Summary of Results and Challenges

During the first reporting period (M03–M18), WP4 achieved substantial progress toward the development of an integrated intelligent monitoring framework capable of supporting real-time road safety, behavioural interpretation, environmental analysis and predictive maintenance. All tasks delivered preliminary (v1) implementations that underwent internal validation using benchmark datasets and early pilot-related recordings. The outcomes demonstrate strong alignment with the project's Key Results (KR) and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), providing a solid basis for the upcoming integration and pilot activities planned for M22–M26.

Task 4.1 produced a complete real-time edge-processing pipeline integrating object detection, multi-target tracking and video stabilisation. Optimisation efforts – such as parallelisation, module decoupling and model quantisation – significantly increased throughput on constrained hardware platforms. The system achieved real-time performance with approximately 11 FPS on NVIDIA Jetson devices and 25 FPS on GPU-based systems. The detection models now cover more than fifteen object categories, exceeding KPI4.1, and early accuracy results (80–88% mAP for YOLOv8/YOLOv11) confirm compliance with KPI4.2.

In Task 4.2, a unified behavioural analysis framework was implemented and integrated within the Kafka streaming infrastructure. Three behavioural detectors – zebra-crossing violations, improper lane usage and failure to yield – were developed and validated on simulated environments, achieving accuracy scores of 80–87%. Additional prototype detectors for red-light violations, cyclist hand signalling and abrupt movements were created and will be further refined as annotated pilot data becomes available. A multimodal architecture was also designed to combine trajectory information with contextual scene semantics, enabling richer understanding of hazardous behaviours.

Task 4.3 focused on automated road-defect detection and delivered a robust pipeline based on YOLOv11 models. The system operated in real time at 22–27 FPS and achieved 78–85% mAP on combined RDD2022 and InfraPlan datasets. The integration of EigenCAM improved interpretability and enabled seamless use of detection outputs within both the Digital Twin and the 3D reconstruction workflow. Metadata structures and severity-estimation logic were introduced to support prioritised road maintenance. Performance is already close to KPI13.1 and KPI13.2, establishing a solid basis for further optimisation.

In Task 4.4, a fully containerised WRF/WRFDA ecosystem was deployed for the Thessaloniki and Karlovac pilot sites. High-resolution environmental domains and physics parametrisations were configured, and continuous access to observational data was ensured through municipal APIs and Weather Underground sources. This addressed initial gaps in local data availability. Initial KPIs for data quality, model

readiness and monitoring reliability were established to support the development of the WP4 hazard-alert pipeline.

Finally, Task 4.5 achieved major advances in AI-driven 3D scene reconstruction. Using Splatfacto (3D Gaussian Splatting), the team produced high-fidelity 3D representations validated on benchmark datasets such as Mip-NeRF 360 and on custom UAV imagery. Reconstructions of potholes and complex traffic scenarios exhibited strong geometric consistency and photorealistic rendering. Large-scale tests with H3DGS confirmed the feasibility of processing extended road segments. For the first time, semantic information based on EigenCAM activations from Task 4.3 was incorporated into the 3D pipeline, enabling enriched safety-oriented 3D environments.

While WP4 progressed strongly, several challenges affected the pace of validation. The absence of real annotated datasets from the Nevers, Graz and Alba Iulia pilots required reliance on simulated and public datasets, particularly impacting Tasks 4.2 and 4.3. This was mitigated through rehearsal datasets, harmonised annotation guidelines and early data-sharing procedures. Environmental variability – such as rain, glare, shadows, and low-light conditions – continued to challenge visual models, prompting expanded datasets, environment-aware augmentation strategies and plans for systematic pilot-site testing. Computational constraints on edge devices also required careful optimisation, as some higher-capacity models remain demanding for embedded hardware. Behavioural modelling dependencies on scenario-specific geometries, coupled with incomplete early pilot mapping data, delayed the development of universal configuration templates. Finally, the integration of heterogeneous WP4 modules – spanning detection, tracking, 3D reconstruction, weather modelling and streaming – requires close coordination with WP3 and WP5 to ensure consistency in metadata, schemas and timing.

Overall, despite these challenges, WP4 remains on track. The preliminary implementations demonstrate strong technical maturity and readiness for integration, positioning the work package to deliver fully operational monitoring capabilities during the next project phase.

5 Conclusions and Next Steps

The first reporting period has confirmed the technical feasibility and maturity of the intelligent monitoring components developed within WP4. The work carried out between M03 and M18 demonstrates that the project has established a robust foundation for real-time analysis of road infrastructure, behavioural events, environmental conditions and 3D scene understanding. Preliminary results validate the selected methodologies, show strong alignment with the defined KPIs, and highlight the potential of the WP4 technologies to significantly improve road safety and maintenance operations.

The progress made across Tasks 4.1 to 4.5 provides a coherent set of interoperable modules that will form the basis of the integrated monitoring framework. Although several challenges remain – primarily related to data availability, environmental variability and edge-device limitations – mitigation strategies have been put in place, and the consortium is now well positioned to accelerate validation activities as soon as real pilot data becomes available. Integration with WP3 (data acquisition and communication) and WP5 (digital twins and predictive models) will be a central focus of the next phase.

In conclusion, WP4 is progressing on schedule and has delivered strong, measurable achievements that demonstrate both technical depth and system-wide relevance. The next period will focus on consolidating these advancements, ensuring full operational integration, and validating the technologies in the project's real-world pilots to realise their full impact within the iDriving ecosystem.

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iDRIVING

Intelligent & Digital Roadway Infrastructure for Vehicles Integrated with Next-Gen Technologies

PROJECT FACTS

Start date: 01/07/2024 **Duration:** 36M **Call:** HORIZON-CL5-2023-D6-01 **Total cost:** € 4,998,733.75 **Coordinator:** Ethniko Kentro Erevnas kai Technologikis Anaptyxis (CERTH).

iDriving Consortium

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